

INVESTIGATING THE ISSUE OF CORRUPTION IN NIYI OSUNDARE'S *THE STATE VISIT*

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Abstract

This study investigates an expository discourse on corruption tendencies among Nigerian leaders as represented in Niyi Osundare's *The State Visit*. It examines the historical context of the play, constituting an imaginary version of the real political event of the society it represented. This study adopts the theories of Postcolonialism and New Historicism, to investigate the issues of economic exploitation, social disparity, and dialectal materialism that form the locus of the play. A close reading of the characters in the play reveals cases of political oppression, tyranny, corruption, poverty and revolutionary struggle for a more improved society. By implication, members of the oppressed class take some radical steps to redeem themselves. Niyi Osundare's *The State Visit* exposes the behaviour of the political class. It also explores issues of corruption, acquiescence, assent and compliance or defiance, protest and revolt as actions and counter-actions against the political space, as well as the nature of the relationship between a society and its leadership. Findings reveal that the play is reflective of Nigerian political history as the masses are found engaging in riots, strikes and demonstrations against the ruling government and the playwright reveals that the poor socioeconomic condition of the Nigerian masses is triggered by the recurrent exploitation and brazen corruption manifested by the politicians.

Keywords: Corruption, Leadership, Masses, Politics, Class.

Introduction

Apparently, from the colonial to post-colonial period, literary contributions from Nigeria have been invaluable and impressively committed to societal concerns. Dominantly among them is the issue of socio-political insurrection and the quest for political change. No wonder Eurocentric critics regard African literary expressions as anthropological, situational and characteristic of "protest literature" that is filled with a "constant moral attitude" (Chinweizu et al, 1980: 7). As such, an African writer reacts to

the prevailing socio-political pressures and upheavals in his or her environment (Soyinka, 1968; Achebe, 1975; Wa Thiong'o 1981; Umukoro 1994; Bamidele 2003). In fact, from the works of the pioneers to the contemporary, the tenor of social and/ or socialist commitments constitutes the thrust of Nigerian literature.

Nonetheless, the evolving phases in African history— Pre-colonial, Colonial and Post-colonial— have greatly affected or influenced the African writers' literary outputs. For instance, during the colonial era, the writers' concerns revolved around the reconstruction of Africa's image, distorted and bruised by colonial intrusion. However, since independence, their concerns have shifted towards the area of social criticism (attacking and exposing injustice). Their works thus, become a tool for addressing socio-political abnormalities, especially corruption, in their respective countries and Africa at large. This role has later turned to "acting" rather than reacting.

According to Transparency International quoted in Amundsen (1999:1), "Corruption is one of the greatest challenges of the contemporary world. It undermines governance, fundamentally distorts public policy, leads to the misallocation of resources, harms the public sector and private sector development and particularly hurts the poor". Moreover, Amundsen (1999:1) in his words says "Corruption is a disease, cancer that eats into the cultural, political and economic fabrics of society, and destroys the functioning of vital organs". In contemporary Nigeria, corruption is perhaps the major threat to the proper administration of the country. However, as important social properties, Arts play an invaluable role in the sustenance of the lore, mores and the general ways of life of the people. As affirmed by Wole Soyinka (1968: 21), "The artist has always functioned in African society as the record of the mores and experience of his society and as the voice of vision in his own time". For instance, from the Hubert Ogunde tradition to the writings of J. P. Clark, Wole Soyinka, Ola Rotimi, Femi Osofisan, Olu Obafemi, Niyi Osundare, Stephen Kekeghe, Soji Cole and many other contemporary playwrights, the dehumanization encountered in civilian and military rule are persistently revisited.

Similarly, Ngugi wa Thiongo (1981) asserts that there is a dialectal nexus between literature and politics as they "are reflected in one another and can act on one another". Bringing this dialectal relationship to the ambit of drama or play in Nigeria, Umukoro (1994) notes that politics, no doubt, is the most obvious subject for the Nigerian playwright since the playwright's vision is anchored on the enthronement of regenerative political ideas. As such, many Nigerian plays dwell on the crises of the political system and leadership, especially corruption, to make suggestions for social redemption. It is in this regard that this study explores Nigerian Drama from the perspective of its political value. It pays close attention to characters and situations in Osundare's *The State Visit*, to analyse corruption, which Nigerian dramatists propose in their works for a new democratic society. It investigates how the Nigerian playwright, Niyi Osundare, has used politics as a mode of assessing the relationship between art, ideology, politics and social consciousness. This involves an examination of the craft of drama as it tries to show how those political views are reflected through a variety of methods.

Conceptualizing Corruption

To enhance clarity and precision in the understanding of corruption in the ambit of Nigeria, it becomes necessary to conceptualize the idea. Over the years, several scholars and organisations have described corruption from different perspectives in their various literature. Transparency International (2008) defines corruption as "the abuse of public office or entrusted power for private gains". This definition views corruption as an act perpetrated by a public officeholder or someone who controls power. Similarly, Mike (2022) defines corruption as dishonest or fraudulent conduct by those in power, typically involving bribes. Again, corruption is perceived as the process whereby an official demands and receives a bribe before performing any official task assigned to him. Furthermore, Huntington (1968) as cited in Obasanjo (2013) described corruption as the behaviour of public officials that deviates from accepted norms to serve a private end. In the same vein, Stapenhurst & Sedigh (1999) as cited in Obasanjo (2013) state that corruption is the abuse of power, most often for personal gain or for the benefit of a group to which one owes allegiance. Corruption can be motivated by greed, the desire to retain or increase one's power, or perversely enough, by the desire to maintain a supposed greater good. Critically examining the definitions of corruption considered so far, it could be inferred that corruption is common among public officeholders who selfishly aim at diverting public resources for their gains.

It is indisputable that the effect of corruption on any community of people or nation is significant. It is in this vein that Ogboru (2009) asserts that "Corruption is the illegal profiteering (mismanagement of public funds) by a public officer from his/her position as a representative of the government. It wastes resources, distorts budgetary allocation, breeds inefficiency and unpredictability, slows and erodes development and lowers respect for constituted authority". Ogboru's (2009) definition also illustrates the fact that corruption is illegal and as such, its perpetrators achieve their goals through systematic and crafty means. This is why Dikwa (2016) opines that corruption is a systematic vice associated with an individual, society or nation which reflects favouritism, nepotism, tribalism, sectionalism, undue enrichment, amassing of wealth, abuse of office, power, position, and derivation of undue gains and benefits. He also reflects on the different forms and shapes that corruption could take when he notes that corruption includes bribery, smuggling, fraud, illegal payments, money laundering, drug trafficking, falsification of documents and records, window dressing, false declaration, evasion, overpayment, underpayment, deceit, forgery, concealment, aiding and abetting of any kind to the detriment of another person, community, society or nation (Dikwa, 2016).

Without any doubt, the idea of corruption has been studied in several scholarly works, not only from an economic standpoint but also through the lenses of literary works. However, the subject of corruption is so broad that different scholars can approach it from different perspectives and with fresh insights. Thus, this study is a new dimension into the examination of corruption from a literary view. It examines the relationship of the context of *The State Visit* with the evaluation of how Osundare delineates the socio-political vices of corruption, maladministration and unemployment in Nigeria, while still being a literary artist, using literature as a tool of reformation for the troubled society.

Theoretical Consideration

The theories of Postcolonialism and New Historicism are adopted for a proper study of the issue of corruption in Niyi Osundare's *The State Visit*. When it was conceived, Postcolonialism or the Postcolonial Theory was conceived as an anti-colonial ideology; geared towards attacking colonial perceptions, practices and discourses on the subject of the colonised. Nonetheless, in more recent literature, scholars have effected several modifications as regards what the theory encompasses as a result of the different experiences of various formerly colonised countries in the contemporary world.

According to Ashcroft et al (1989), the postcolonial theory emerges “from the inability of European theory” to properly address the challenges and the hybridity of cultural provenance of postcolonial writings. This implies that the Postcolonial Theory is meant to dwell on the experiences of formerly colonised countries as captured in the works of their writers. It is to this end that Olaniyan and Kehinde (2024) citing Tyson (1999), note that the "Postcolonial theory postulates hypothetical assumptions and socio-political concerns on the experience and literary production of formerly colonised peoples whose history is characterised by extreme political, social, and psychological dislocation and oppression." This underscores the fact that the Postcolonial theory is not meant to examine only purely anti-colonial works but also those that capture the political, economic, social and even religious realities of these formerly colonised countries since their independence, with a focus on internal contributory factors, rather than external.

New Historicism is a literary theory that emerged in the 1980s, emphasizing the relationship between literature and its historical context (Greenblatt, 2000). Renu Paul Ukkan (2004:23-24) notes that “New Historicism involves a parallel reading or juxtaposition of the literary and the non-literary text of the same historical period. Both are given equal importance and allowed to work as sources of information and interrogation with each other”. This implies that New Historicism studies the interface of a literary text and history (non-literary). John Brannigan (1998) explains that New Historicism views history as one of the ways societies construct narratives that unconsciously fit their interests. Hence, the Postcolonial Theory and New Historicism would efficiently help to study the issue of corruption in Niyi Osundare's *The State Visit*. While Postcolonialism would help to examine the forces behind the depth of corruption as portrayed in the play, New Historicism would help to situate this study in the historical ambit of the play.

Plot Synopsis of *The State Visit*

All the events in the play surround preparations for a state visit. The play opens with the Narrator embarking on an extensive discussion of the rot and madness of men that characterize the government machinery in Yakeland. The meeting of the state cabinet began with the Head of State or Head, presiding. The subject of the discussion is the impending visit of the Head of Wilama, a leader of a neighbouring country, and the preparation to accord him a befitting reception.

The cabinet meeting itself exposes the Head and his ministers as unserious minds, for all that they talk about is how to divert public funds to provide essential services to the state visit. Meanwhile, the land is experiencing drought, a decline in

national earnings and the discontent of the populace. It is decided that the six hundred million naira for the maize project be diverted to planning the state visit against the counsel of the finance minister, the only voice of reason in the cabinet.

We later encounter the beggars in front of a supermarket. The beggars include Sule, Etim, Obi and Abeke. They all recount their tales of woe, all pointing to the fact that they are victims of the insensitivity of society to the plight of the common people. Order is later given that they are cleared from the streets in preparation for the visit. When the cabinet meeting resumes, the uncooperative finance minister has been replaced. Reports are also taken as to the preparation for the visit. The cabinet is assured of the co-operation of the 'Daily Gist' that has been paid to ensure good media coverage and the opposition of the 'Telling Tempo'.

A few people appear before the council. First is the service Professor, who is gladly serving as the speech writer of the Head of State. Then comes Medal Smith, who is mandated to decorate the ceremonial coat of the Head. After him comes the Paint, who turns out to be confrontational, insisting on not working for or collaborating with a tyrannical government. He affirms his allegiance to the truth, and he is ordered to be taken out. Colonel, who is in charge of traffic, is the next to appear. He justifies their preference for instant punishment for lawless motorists and other road users as opposed to the alternative of trying them according to the law.

The next act presents a rally of workers and students where they narrate their woes and affirm their opposition to the senseless arrangement for the state visit of the Head of Wilama. As usual, their gathering is declared unlawful and dispersed by the police. The narrator then appears again to thank the audience and to draw their attention to the issues that are raised in the play. He concludes that the drama of opposition to the bad government of the land has just started.

Textual Representation of Corruption in Niyi Osundare's *The State Visit*

Niyi Osundare in the play *The State Visit* delves into the socio-political history of Yanke, an imaginary country in the African continent, which could be synonymous with the country Nigeria. In this literary work, political leaders or rulers see themselves as the lords and masters of the people. This event may be situated between the mid-1980s' and the late 1990s' when military rule was the phenomenon in Nigeria before the emergence of the country's democracy in 1999. Between these periods, military dictators in collaboration with their civilian counterparts ensured constant impoverishment of the people as the 'milk and honey' of the land only enriched a few purses. Osundare employed the use of a narrator to open the play with what can be termed a summary of the Yanke's country. The narrator introduces the play to the audience, and at the same time prepares their sight, and senses for foreshadowing. The narrator describes the country as a land of two rivers. This is a pointer that Yanke Country and Nigeria are likely the same. From the narrative technique adopted in the opening scene, the corruptness of the leadership of Yanke is brought to the fore as the people are said to live in abject poverty even though the land is blessed with milk and honey. According to the narrator, 'There is a land of two rivers, a land blessed with milk and honey, the softest and the healthiest of sunshine. But a few men fouled up the milk and mixed the honey

with cow dung. Men who have the power to act and not be questioned: men who measure their height by the genuflection of others. (Osundare: 9).

The country is no doubt bestowed with several natural resources as the country is said to be “rich in everything”. The wealth of the land is, however, with the few bourgeoisies. These resources are however not enjoyed by all unfortunately as it is being plundered and mismanaged by the rulers, who have found it convenient to foul up the milk and mix the honey with cow dung to distract others from wanting to taste it. The only thing in abundance with the masses is poverty, while the wealthy continue to fester in opulence. The narrator describes these rulers as men whose actions cannot be questioned as they rule by the gun unlike in democracy, where there is freedom of expression. These men, it is also revealed, measure how tall they are by the obeisance of others to them; the more the people that pay tributes to them, the better their ego.

The narrator also reveals to the reader (audience) that the country is sick, as almost every sector of the society is corrupt. He starts with the Medical Doctor who is said to collect egg bribes from Kwashiorkor patients (egg is on their own a source of nutrients, so how can they get cured when what they should eat to cure their ailment is being taken from them?). Also, the journalist has turned into a “minion for looting” as he is paid to write all forms of lies and to rewrite history as constantly as he is induced with bribery. The business persons are also not left out of the corrupt practices, as they stand between the masses and progress by “buying cheap and selling beer, smuggling, hoarding, extorting, and crushing under the weight of profit”. The chief corrupt officers of the country, the Police, also flog bribes out of “mere suspects”, while port workers also make cargoes disappear through the trick of talisman. The Judicial officers (Judges/magistrates) would rather ‘count justice in notes and coins’ (Osundare: 11).

The list of corrupt people is inexhaustible. The Clergymen (Pastors and Imams) who should be propagators of sinless living and prophets of hope have joined the wagon as they swallow the widow’s mite just like Brother Jeroboam in Soyinka’s *The Trials of Brother Jero*. The teachers and lecturers, who should teach against corruption, are not seen to fare any better as they will rather trade being in the classroom for political appointments on boards of government parastatals, agencies or ministries, induce money out of students or seek sexual gratifications from them. The narrator also says that aside from these corrupt characters, several characters are also aware of the existing corruption but would rather see it as a design of God; some would not bother to stir as they are comfortable with their present position. With the employment of the narrator, Osundare from the outset reveals to us the socio-political melancholy the country is steeped in. The level of corruption in the country is staggering and the economic squalor is enormous. The military ruling government in the play is a mixture of both military and civilian leaders whose sole aim is to ensure that they amass as much wealth as possible for themselves and their immediate families. The play starts with a cabinet meeting in an atmosphere of opulence, deceit, insincerity, and gross corruption. The subject of discussion further reveals the degradation that has eaten deep into society – a visit by another corrupt leader of a neighbouring country. Cabinet meetings are depicted as opportunities to foster their nests and discuss very irrelevant issues like a state visit when the country is threatened by a drought. The contributions of their leaders to important national issues are usually very shallow, thereby displaying their level of intelligence and

literacy. The Head of State popularly called “Head” starts the meeting by announcing the planned visit of a brother Head of State from the Republic of Wilama. The description of the expected visitor confirms him to be a dictator to the core even though Head describes him as a benevolent leader. This leader of Wilama is of the view that all forms of opposition must be crushed, as they constitute a threat to the government. He therefore orders the burning down of unfriendly media houses and ‘dumped vocal critics in some safe prison ...’ (Osundare: 13). He bans the parliament, as he prefers ‘...the direct rule of his family to the endless bickering of that house of words where the only thing that gets done is nothing...’ He also ‘commanded each tribal chief to donate a virgin to his royal harem.’ (Osundare: 13). These descriptions give a vivid prototype of military leadership in Africa.

Osundare has exclusively captured the high level of corruption in Africa in the opening scene of the play alone. Before venturing further into the play, you already know the kind of characters to expect – ridiculously corrupt leaders. The corruption is not however with the leadership alone, as the scarcity of virgins also confirms the moral decadence among the youths (especially the females) in the society. Greedy fathers have given their daughters to these autocratic leaders. The leadership of the nation cares less about the people they govern and only does as it pleases and suites them. After several options like spending everything in the coffers and borrowing more from a friendly country like America and printing more currency by decree had been fully argued and exhausted, it was eventually agreed to divert the funds meant for the Maize project to host the state visit. Though this action will bring untold hardship to the masses of Yankee and prolong days of hunger, poverty, deprivation and want as the Maize Fund was strategically borrowed to prevent drought, the country’s main cause of shortage in food production, the leaders are not at all bothered about the plight of the masses. It has become a pattern to continually divert funds originally meant for poverty eradication projects for trivial issues without consideration for what consequences their actions will trigger. ‘. . . It has happened before. Remember the money for our water Dam project was diverted to the funeral of our leader’s grandfather. After all, it was the people who ate the food and drank the wine’ (Osundare: 19).

The State Visit delves into contemporary socio-political history in which rulers have presented themselves as lords and dictators to the ruled. The play is set in Yankee, an imaginary African country where “the rulers, like lions, prey on the ruled”. It is not known where Yankee is on the African continent, but the unfolding events from recent socio-political history point to the fact that the imaginary state of Yankee could be Nigeria. It could also be any part of the continent where both civilian and military dictators in collaboration with compromising and sycophant civilians, ensure that the military fester in opulence, while the poor continue to squirm in their poverty. This was witnessed during the military regime of General Ibrahim Gbadamosi Babangida and General Sanni Abacha.

The narrator in the opening of the play paints an image of the type of country the playwright had in mind:

There is a land of two rivers, A land blessed with milk and honey, the softest and the healthiest of sunshine. But few men fouled up the milk and mixed the honey with cow dung. Men who have the power to act and

not be questioned: men who measure their height by the genuflection of others. (2002:9)

The narrator's statement that the land is "blessed with milk and honey, with the softest and the wealthiest of sunshine" refers to the natural resources available in Yankee, (i.e. Rivers Niger and Benue in Nigeria). However, the milk and honey have been mixed with 'cow dung', implying that the country's potential for prosperity has been soiled by a few men who hold absolute power.

In the play, the pattern of social stratification in most African states as represented by Yankee is made plain. The "Head" speaking to his cabinet revealed the existence of two distinct classes, 'the ruler and the ruled', when he says: "Who are the people when we talk about the government? What are they... Well the people may do what they like" (p.22). Such reckless utterances were witnessed mostly in Nigeria during the inglorious and despotic regimes of the military between 1983 and 1999. Indeed, the former Minister of Communication during General Babangida's regime, Col. David Mark, was quoted to have said that "telephone is not meant for the poor", that is, the masses they were ruling over.

The painter, representing all creative personalities (writers, critics, scholars, etc), rejects to work for the Lion of Yanke land and fearlessly calls the entire cabinet derogatory names to their faces. He refers to them as tyrants and vampires but the Head chooses to remain unperturbed, not understanding what is being echoed. When the cabinet finally realize the "artistic" insults of the painter, their ensuing rage brings about the death of the painter.

The above statement delineates the society of Yankee along the lines of the governors and the governed and shows how the leaders hold the people in contempt. The language/speech smacks of arrogance. The ruling upper class subdues the masses by employing the instruments of exploitation and alienation through state apparatus to deny the proletariat their rights as humans. An example of such exploitation is the transfer of six million Arina meant for the maize project to the welcome party for the visiting president of Wilama. Little wonder that the narrator in his opening statement remarks that the state of Yankee is enmeshed in corruption, sick and seriously in need of salvation.

The ruling government of Yankee is an admixture of military and civilian political leaders. Oftentimes, when the military truncates the democratic process in Africa, they wield absolute power and also secure their positions with the full support of civilian cohorts whose aim as observed in *The State Visit* is to enjoy personal benefits. The poor masses of Yankee represent the proletariats, who have been denied all rights to decent living and economic prosperity. What is even more, the cabinet meeting opens in an atmosphere that depicts society as one polarized along class lines. The discussion at the meeting indicates the level of unseriousness the leaders of Yankee attach to governance as the meeting becomes an avenue to discuss extraneous issues.

The contributions of cabinet members to serious national issues are often very shallow, thereby displaying their ignorance and incompetence. The 'Head' informs his cabinet members of the impending visit of his 'brother' head of another general' from the Republic of Wilama The 'Head' describes his visiting brother as a "benevolent leader" of his people who "banned parliament, preferring the direct rule of his family... He

imported a teacher from a Manchester high school in England to head the only University in the country... (p.13).

The above statement presents a vivid image of the president of Wilama, the leader whom the Yankee leadership intends to host with the people's money. It sums up the pedigree of the leader who trivializes the education of his people by importing a high school teacher from Manchester England to head his nation's university. While there was no controversy concerning the rationale behind the hosting, the major concern is how to fund the state visit. The cabinet is at a loss and deliberating on how to fund the state visit in the face of a battered and collapsed economy. Just as the entire cabinet ratifies the suggestion that the five million Arina left in the Treasury be deployed towards the hosting, they are rather shocked to hear that the same money has been diverted to buy a jet fighter even when the country is not at war and has not received any territorial threat. However, the search for a hosting fund did not go far as the Minister of Public Morality suggests the Six Million Arina maize fund project donated by the World Food Programme as the way out. The final speech of the Head at the last cabinet meeting confirms that as long as Nigeria continues to have insincere leaders and sycophants in power, the people shall continually have corruption and poverty to tackle:

Thank you, my people, for your patience and understanding. With assets like you around me, I can boast that I have the wisest, truest, most thoughtful and most corruptible – eh . . . eh... incorruptible cabinet in Africa. (63)

The resistance from the people of Yanke land is severe and the Cabinet grapples with how to overcome all opposition. Every stratum of the society condemns the diversion of the Maize Fund for a mere 'State Visit'; thus, a protest is staged. The youths, aged, students, workers, market men and women all take to the street to drive home their grievances. The following passage underscores the revolutionary tenor of the protesters:

PLACARDS: GIVE US FOOD, NOT WHIPS!

WHERE HAS THE MAIZE FUND GONE?

MONKEY THEY WORK, BABOON DEY CHOP

WHERE ARE OUR DISAPPEARED COMRADES?

DOWN WITH DICTATORSHIP

WE ARE ALL BORN EQUAL

SONG: We build the house for all to live

They cast us out into the street

We kill the beast with our tiny stones

They eat and throw us bones

We build the house with sweat and pains

They fill our lives with chains

So join your hands, kill the lion, Burn evil with hot iron (64).

In present-day Nigeria, it is not just the Maize Funds that are diverted but all sorts of funds: Agricultural funds, Kerosene and Petroleum subsidy funds, Pensions funds, Education funds, Water project funds and so on. The present suspension of the Attorney General of the Federation, Justice Onoghen is still raising specks of dust while

several others before it have been laid to rest without any proper resolution proffered. The immediate past Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria is another reference point. In the play, the protest takes a new dimension at the arrival of the Police Inspector, who attempts to disperse the gathered protesters. The choice of words used by the Inspector in praise of the ruler only aggravates and infuriates the people the more; this leads to a clash between the protesters and the Police, leading to loss of lives. As the narrator comes back again to conclude the play, Osundare confirms that the play is only a re-enactment of a dream, 'a dream plucked from the tinsel glitter of powerful thrones'. However, the looting continues, and corruption is taking other forms thus the fight must also be reinvigorated.

Further economic exploration is reflected in the manner the leaders of Yankee expend Millions of Arina on white elephant projects. A good example is the diversion of state funds by the Head to the burial of his grandfather (p.19). The economic exploitation not only enslaves the masses but keeps them perpetually subservient to the ruling class. The beggars of Yankee as represented by: Sule, Etim, Abeke and Obi have been permanently subjected to life on the streets. The attendant effects of the dictatorial conduct of Yankee leaders rage as the Head and other cabinet members seem to, daily, enact new and more ingenious ways of ensuring the perpetual exploitation of the masses. The beggars are on the lower rung of the social ladder not because they are not enterprising, but because they are encumbered by the limited opportunities that society makes available for them. The experiences of the beggars differ from person to person. Abeke, for instance, gave birth to an unwanted child after she was kidnapped and raped by a wealthy man (p.34). The misery of the beggars is further heightened when they are eventually sent off the street of Yankee in preparation for the hosting of the visiting Head of Wilama.

Religious leaders also aid and abet Yankee rulers as both the Archbishop and the Chief Imam promised their presence at the interdenominational Service for the visitor while also assuring the Head of God's support for his leadership (p.55).

To confront the hydra-headed monster of misgovernance in Yankee, the opposition offers resistance to save society from total collapse. Resistance from the opposition rages with the youth group, students and workers demonstrating on the streets.

The painter on the other hand engages the Head and other members of his cabinet, by withholding his professional services. He refuses to paint a portrait for the Head. Thus, the people of Yankee led by the Finance Minister (who had earlier resigned from office) and some other voices of dissent rose against the government's act of insensibility and general maladministration. The government, however, responds to those voices of dissent with brutality. The revolution in *The State Visit* can be likened to the revolutions witnessed some time ago in Northern African countries like Egypt, Tunisia and Libya where the leaders of both Egypt and Tunisia were sacked and the Libya leader was killed as he held on to power tenaciously.

Conclusion

The State visit by Niyi Osundare is a realistic depiction of the nature of corruption in Nigeria and how Nigerian leaders have been exploiting her citizens. Niyi Osundare revealed that the main goal of Nigerian leaders in government is to enrich themselves. He, therefore, portrays Nigerian leaders as corrupt, selfish and backward who

deploy thuggery and violence in manipulating election results to their favour. However, to highlight the poor political visions and corrupt nature of the emergent political leaders towards building the Nigeria nation-state is not to deny some important contributions they have made to the foundation and development of Nigeria. For one thing, they kept Nigeria as an entity. For another, the Nigerian nation is still in existence and has potential and opportunities for greatness, if only her leaders could guide her in the right direction and or allow the youths to rise to challenge the status quo as witnessed in *The State Visit*.

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